

A NOTE ON DICHLORO-ANTIMONY 8-HYDROXYQUINOLATE

BY R. K. PATTANAİK AND S. PANI

A saturated aqueous solution of antimony chloride contains approximately 72 g. mol. of antimony chloride in 100 g. mol. of water. There is evidence that the solution consists of aquo-trichloro-antimony and to a small extent hydroxo-trichloro-antimonite complexes (this *issue*, p. 532). If the above complexes actually exist in the solution it would be possible to replace the water molecule (or the hydroxyl ion) and some or all of the chlorine by powerful donor groups. To verify this, investigations were undertaken in two different directions. Ammonia and amines like pyridine etc. have comparatively high co-ordinating power and can replace water or chlorine from co-ordination sphere. It might therefore be possible to replace the water molecule or even the chlorine atoms by ammonia or amines. A pyridine complex, which has been prepared, is described in another note (this *issue*, p. 538).

It is known that bidentate chelates can replace two groups from the co-ordination sphere due to the formation of five- or six- membered ring. Attempts were therefore made to prepare 8-hydroxyquinolate complex of antimony. The compounds $\text{Sb}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ON})_3$ and $\text{SbO}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ON})_2 \cdot \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ON}$ have already been reported by Pirtea (*Z. anal. Chem.* 1939, 118, 26).

The reagents used were of Analar quality. To nearly 2 c. c. of a saturated aqueous solution of antimony chloride a small amount of solid 8-hydroxyquinoline was added when an immediate reaction started with the separation of yellow solid (excess of 8-hydroxyquinoline was avoided). It was then gently heated and a clear homogeneous yellow liquid was obtained. This was cooled under tap when the whole liquid solidified. Antimony chloride and its saturated aqueous solution being highly soluble in ether, the above solid was repeatedly washed with ether to remove any excess of antimony chloride, and dried in vacuum (H_2SO_4).

It is a yellow solid, not hydrolysed by water immediately. When heated it melts to a reddish liquid which on cooling solidifies to a yellowish brown product, probably due to partial decomposition. It dissolves in HCl (conc.) and is decomposed by alkali.

The compound was analysed as described in the previous paper. The results are shown below.

TABLE I

	Found.	Calc. for
Antimony	35.97 % 35.93	36.5%
Chlorine	20.93 20.68	21.13
8-Hydroxyquinoline	41.43	42.85

